

Original Article

Improving Career Guidance and Counselling in Universities: A Qualitative Investigation from Pakistan

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Abstract

Guidance and counseling are highly beneficial for university students. Some Pakistani universities offer career guidance and counseling (CGC) but there is a huge room for improvement. This study explored various ways to improve CGC in Pakistani universities. Qualitative investigation was carried out by conducting semi-structured interviews with university students and career service providers. Interview data was transcribed and analyzed by thematic analysis. Twelve themes were identified which showed various steps to be taken by students, career service providers, university management, employers from industry and government. People should be made aware and accepting of CGC; policies should be made and funds should be allocated for CGC; services should be diversified, approachable and delivered by professionals; available services and events should be rigorously marketed, regularly conducted and mandatory to attend; CGC should focus on entrepreneurship, skill development and bridging the academia-industry gap. Combined efforts by multiple stake holders particularly students and service providers would be vital for bringing the necessary improvements in CGC. Implications, recommendations and limitations are also discussed at the end.

Keywords: improvement; career guidance; career counselling; qualitative

INTRODUCTION

Career guidance and counseling (CGC) includes guidance and help for career related issues of people. CGC could be useful for selecting educational pathway, deciding occupation, choosing a job, getting required training, making right decisions etc. It could be offered to individuals or groups. It could help a wide range of people from high-school kids to retired individuals. But most CGC is offered to school leavers or university students as number of important decisions are to be made at those transitory periods of life. School leavers usually want to join worthy institutions for continuing their education whereas university students are preparing to enter the world of work. CGC could be of great use to them, particularly university students, as numerous career concerns could be resolved by CGC and smooth transitions could be made from education to work. CGC is therefore highly needed but not well-developed in Pakistan. Over the years, efforts have increased to offer more and better CGC but there is still a long way to go. Therefore, we want to explore different ways to bring betterment in CGC in Pakistani universities.

LITERATURE REVIEW

Research studies have looked at various aspects of CGC. The significance, process, demand and benefits have been highlighted in previous literature, particularly international researches. A study by Cojocariu and Puiu, (2014) emphasized the importance and integration of CGC in academic life of students. CGC should be integrated into university life of students from the beginning till the very end of their university degree. CGC services should work on enhancing students' personal as well as professional knowledge and align theory with practice in their degree programs. Some problems commonly faced in CGC process were also highlighted like lack of students' interest and involvement in career services, insufficient number of university level CSPs, and fewer job openings for fresh graduates.

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According to the demands of the modern day world, careers have also changed immensely. Lifelong nature of careers and the necessary changes in CGC process were accentuated by researchers Litoiu and Oproiu (2012). CGC is no longer a one-time activity. With the changing world, CGC has also changed and now many factors come into play; multiple academic and professional choices are involved. Appropriate focus should be given to furthering students' abilities and potentials by introducing practical approach in their theoretical education. CGC should also be initiated early instead of delaying it to the final year of university. CGC should also offer early career planning and not just rely on typical CGC services like interview skills, job search, CV writing. Easy access to CGC was pointed out by Sun and Yuen (2012). Their study suggests that instead of imposing foreign concepts and practices of CGC on local students, foreign models and theories should be indigenized for best results with university students. National and local policies should endorse career service provision at educational institutions. Successful implementation of effective career services at university level is the need of the hour and could be achieved through systematic efforts.

Research about university level CGC is not excessive in Pakistan, though the number of studies is increasing over the years. A possible reason for little research is evident in Richard's (2005) work that countries with low-economic development have limited research in CGC as the major struggle in those countries is survival of the person instead of growth and development of the person. A study conducted in Islamabad found CGC to be of high value but low utility for university students. Proper system for career counseling was non-existent in educational institutions of the country. Students chose their academics and their careers based on parental influence, peer influence and lack of information about other opportunities. Parents, teachers and friends acted as sources of career advice and guidance. In some universities, placement offices were present but they were not a proper source of career guidance as they failed to develop close interactions with students (Bilal & Malik, 2014).

Need to improve CGC is often stressed in indigenous newspaper articles. Inpaper magazine (2012 March 24) of Dawn newspaper highlighted that CGC should be a key component of our educational system. Career services are important for university students to make right decisions. Other news articles have mentioned that owing to inappropriate CGC services, students pick up academic subjects under peer pressure or parental influence. Lack of career planning leads them to a point where they finish their degrees without any clue regarding employment. Hence, they end up distraught and frustrated. Professional career related services can be helpful in knowing their interests, skills and then matching it up with available career options (Jasmine, 2016 July 30; Farooq, 2016 Nov 12). If students receive the right guidance, they could end up as active and eager economic participants in the country (Khalil, 2011 May 12). The above literature shows that CGC services in Pakistani universities require urgent up gradation.

Policy Review

International countries have specifically devised CGC policies and plans to help their students with career related issues. In England, National Career Service provides information, guidance and advice to students 13 years and older regarding education, training and work opportunities. Qualified career advisers are hired; partnerships are established among educational institutions, volunteer services and professionals so that students can be provided better information regarding world of work (Long & Hubble, 2017). In USA, Office of Career, Technical and Adult Education deals with CGC programs in multiple settings like educational institutions, technical institutions, career centers, correctional centers. Career concerns of people belonging to various ages and backgrounds are resolved by their comprehensive programs (U.S. Department of Education, 2014).

In Germany, National Education Forum in Careers, Education and Employment (2006) provides a network among national and international organizations to offer guidance regarding education, employment and careers. European Centre for the Development of Vocational Training (CEDFOP) states that CGC services should be offered throughout life to fulfill individual needs, societal and economic needs on a larger scale (CEDEFOP, 2009). In Pakistan, specific policy or plan regarding CGC does not exist. However, Pakistan Vision 2025 has emphasized CGC. It has noted that large portion of population consists of youth; so education and skill building is the key to ensure their transition into job market. Lack of these might result in a huge portion of youth being jobless, aimless and hence, dissatisfied. CGC could be vital for providing students with the required help (Ministry of Planning, Development and Reform, 2014).

Pakistan's National Education Policy (2009) points out that a number of challenges and reforms are needed in higher education. Strategic vision in NEP (2009) states that "...employers increasingly look to universities

and colleges to deliver the well-educated workforce they require in the form of articulate, flexible, and readily employable graduates to remain competitive” (Ministry of Education, 2009, p. 57). It implies that educational institutions should offer such services which could guide students regarding career related matters and prepare them for their careers. Hence, CGC must be improved in our country for the demand for CGC services is on the rise.

Theoretical Background

Alderfer (1969) proposed ERG theory of needs which is established upon Maslow’s hierarchy of needs theory. In Alderfer’s theory, needs are categorized into three domains which are labeled as E, R and G. First domain E stands for existence needs. Physical and material needs are included in existence needs like food, clothes, pay benefits. Next domain is R which denotes relatedness needs. Relationships and personal associations are included in relatedness needs like connections with family, colleagues and friends. Last domain is labeled as G and it stands for growth needs. Needs related to personal creativity, development, productivity and utilization of skills are included in it. Appropriate careers can fulfill all these three needs to varied extents. Monetary compensation from one’s career or work can fulfill existence needs; sense of belongingness to one’s career, work, workplace and colleagues can fulfill relatedness needs; being productive at work, reaching one’s potential by expressing one’s skills and abilities at work can fulfill growth needs. However, if a person is stuck or confused in their career, their ERG needs will not be met. While appropriate CGC can do wonders for resolving the issues of such a person, lack of appropriate CGC might cause further hindrances. Consequently, individual might face difficulties in satisfying their ERG needs.

Rationale

In the given age of economic struggles and continuous advancements, well-developed and well managed career is indispensable yet hard to find. People are involved in their career for the major part of the day. But maintaining a strong career is not a smooth sail. Numerous confusions, dilemmas and troubles are faced by the individuals in their careers. Students particularly face this issue during their university life, as they are getting higher education and are entering the world of work in near future. Any help available at that time for their career related concerns can go a long way in sorting out their careers. However, in Pakistan the available career related help is not necessarily as fruitful as one would like it to be. CGC, though flourishing, is not fully established yet. In order to relay the CGC services to students, there is a drastic need to rigorously upgrade CGC services. Better CGC services would likely lead to better CGC related outcomes like employability, economic contribution, self-esteem, mental clarity. In order to reap these benefits in future, authors want to find out the ways to further develop CGC in Pakistan.

Research Objective

This research aimed to find out how CGC could be improved at university level in Pakistan

METHOD

This research studied a previously uninvestigated topic in extensive detail by gathering original interview data; therefore, it is qualitative and exploratory in nature (Guest, MacQueen & Namey, 2014; Stebbins, 2001). Open ended semi-structured interviews were conducted for this purpose. Research has phenomenological orientation as focus was kept on the meanings automatically and naturally surfacing from the interview data instead of operationally defining any terms or concepts beforehand (Lune & Berg, 2017). Research has realist epistemology as it focused on the reality evident in the data (Braun, Clarke & Rance, 2014).

Sampling and sample

Our sample consisted of twenty five individuals including seven CSPs and eighteen students. Respondents belonged to six universities including four private sector universities and two public sector universities which were selected by convenient sampling strategy. CSPs (3 males; 4 females) included in the sample were responsible for the provision of career related help to the students belonging to their institution. Only three CSPs had CGC-related academic qualifications whereas the remaining four had their academic degrees in psychology, business or management. Their CGC-related work experience ranged from 1 to 15 years with a mode value of 2 years. CSPs were purposefully selected for interviews. Students (10 males, 8 females) included in sample belonged to 4-year undergraduate programs. Their ages ranged from 17 to 23 years and they belonged to various semesters ranging from first to eighth. Students were pursuing different degree like management, accounting, psychology, mass communication, and engineering. Only regular students were included; Re-enrolled students, disabled students and

foreign students were excluded. Their socio-economic backgrounds ranged from below average to extremely affluent. Only four students reported to have visited their institution's career office for their career-related concerns. Students were selected through snowball sampling for interviews. Number of respondents and their respective interviews was determined by data saturation. When newly collected data is repeating the information already gathered from the previous data and no original information is coming up, data saturation is said to be achieved (Saunders, Sim, Kingstone, et al., 2018).

Interview Protocol

Interview protocol comprised of a single open-ended question; 'how can CGC be improved in Pakistani universities?' Its sub-questions included 'What improvements could be brought from the students' side/CSPs' side/university's side/industrial side?' To understand the respondent's perspective in detail relevant sub-question or probes were used where required. A single broad question was deemed enough to churn out a detailed response from the interviewee as CGC is a relatively new and developing domain in Pakistan and much could be said in response to a simple open-ended question.

Procedure

After finalizing the research idea, different public and private sector universities from Punjab province of Pakistan were contacted through emails or phone calls. Consent was received after sharing the research purpose and answering any queries. Then primary author visited the universities on pre-settled times and interviewed the CSPs working in those universities. Students were also interviewed from the same universities. Before conducting interview, each respondent was informed about the research purpose and APA's ethical guidelines regarding research like right to withdraw, voluntary participation, confidentiality and safe storage of audio recordings. Informed consent form was also signed by respondents. After data collection, audio recorded interviews were transcribed and analysis was carried out.

Analysis

Transcribed data was analyzed by thematic analysis according to the steps explained by Braun and Clarke (2006). Details are given in table.

Table: Phases and their relevant actions for conducting thematic analysis

Phase	Action
1st Phase: Knowing the data	Interview data was transcribed by researcher and then read three times
2nd Phase: Coming up with codes	On fourth reading of data, possible codes were written down on page margins
3rd Phase: Looking for themes	Codes were gathered into themes
4th Phase: Examining themes	Themes and their relevant verbatims were carefully reviewed
5th Phase: Labeling themes	Theme titles were assigned and themes were further refined
6th Phase: Writing	Penning down the methodology and results in detail

Cautions in thematic analysis. Some cautions were taken during thematic analysis as mentioned by Braun and Clarke (2006). It was made sure that analysis is thorough and not on the basis of few anecdotes. It was also assured that themes were data-driven and well-connected to original research question. Before initiating the analysis, researchers also wrote down potential assumptions in order to box them away and handle the data and analysis objectively.

Addressing credibility (validity) and dependability (reliability)

Multiple steps were taken in order to increase credibility and dependability. The research process, analysis and results were written in a transparent manner as proposed by Guest et al., (2014). Instead of relying on one data source, data triangulation was used as data was gathered from two sources namely students and CSPs. This enhances credibility as well as dependability (Guest et al., 2014). Dependability was further enhanced by dealing with the whole data in the same consistent pattern (Guest et al., 2014). External validity/credibility was addressed by checking the relevance of research findings to other populations, contexts or research studies (Guest et al.,

2014). As most of the findings had support from literature, therefore, it appears to have high external validity/credibility.

RESULTS

The results of analysis are presented and discussed in this section.

Awareness and acceptance

There is a general lack of awareness and acceptance of CGC. Some people are simply unaware of CGC. Some are aware but unwilling to acknowledge their need, and yet there are others who know their need for CGC but they don't get the required service. A student stated *I think people might not have awareness. They should have awareness about career counseling. At least they should have this much awareness (18u)*. So an overall increase in awareness and acceptance of CGC would be wonderful.

Policy making

Appropriate policies would be helpful for improving and promoting CGC. Government should play its role by developing, implementing and supporting relevant policies. It was highlighted by a respondent *Its policy making should be done at the governmental level (C3)*. Supportive policies and steps can go a long way in advancing CGC.

Funding

In order to establish and enhance CGC, it should be provided with more funds. Greater financial resources could be translated into greater number of CSPs, diverse services and better marketing. A respondent emphasized the finances spent on CGC to be a much-needed investment as they commented, *There are two concepts in economics; expense and investment. Spending on career counseling is not an expense at all. It is an investment and its fruitful results will be visible immediately and also in the long term (C3)*.

Expansion of CGC services

CGC services currently offered by universities need to be upgraded. Multiple services should be available at various times during a student's educational journey. It is already mentioned in demographics of students explained under heading Sampling and Sample that many of them never benefitted from any CGC service in their university. One way to develop CGC is profiling students on the basis of their educational background, interests, skills, scores on psychological tests including aptitude tests conducted by university and the degrees they are going to pursue. Appropriate career counseling should be provided during and after this process. A student stated, *At the time of admission an interview should be conducted with a full panel where panelists can properly identify students' strengths. There should be proper (assessment and aptitude) scales regarding that particular field. If the student is fulfilling the pre-requisites (of that field) then they should be allowed to opt for it (18u)*. Some respondents opined that career choices should be guided as per students' aptitude and future industrial requirements instead of blindly supporting students to pursue whatever they are wishing for.

Various CGC services like seminars, talks and group discussions should be conducted. A student commented, *There should be group discussions...there should be at least 1 or 2 seminars or workshops in each semester (12u)*. Using technology based applications can also help to enhance CGC as a CSP said, *They are making an online career helping tool app (in our institution) which will enable the students to do a lot of pre-screening of themselves and their skills, aptitude before they come to career office for further assistance (C5)*. Additionally, one-to-one sessions customized according to the students' needs should also be offered as a CSP emphasized, *When we don't have resources, when there are limited resources then we define a general criteria that every student needs CV writing, interview skills, general counseling, mock interviews. We don't indulge into customization. Career services should be more customized as one student's issue can never be the same as another student's issue (C3)*. Customized CGC should take into account the strong and weak points of that particular individual and build them further.

Publicity and marketing

CGC services should be well-communicated to the students or other prospective users. This will help in increasing its utilization. Poor marketing of CGC was highlighted respondents, *I think they just lack a little bit of publicity... They have this communication barrier from those services to those students who need it...*

lack of publicity, lack of telling people that it exists (2u). Multiple ways can be used for marketing CGC as another respondent said, Social media can be a platform (10u).

Approachable CGC services

CGC centers and offices should be open, inviting and easily approachable for the students. Career offices separate from academic departments might be more approachable for some students as students would be able to contact CSPs without involving their teachers. But some respondents favored the presence of CSP in every department as it might increase the number of students actually meeting the CSP. The bottom line is that CGC services and CSPs should be easy to approach and independent of departmental influence. A student said, *There should be a proper channel in every university for career counseling then I think no student will have to face career problems (18u).* Approachable CGC would elevate the situation of an average student who might not have other resources to help with his/her career related matters.

Professional CSPs

In order to widen the CGC services, it is vital to have teams of professional CSPs. Greater number of professionals will help to cater greater number of students. A student stated, *In our university one problem is that there is just a single person who is handling everything (in the career office). If we want to take appointment (for one to one session) they give appointment after a week. So there should be more (CSPs) (8u).* Additionally, sometimes CGC duties are assigned to teachers randomly. They might not have the relevant knowledge, skill, experience and exposure for the task. Therefore, it is essential to have competent people for CGC. A student mentioned this plight in their comment, *Like (in my institution) a psychologist is needed to cater to a lot of things. A career counselor, who is a professional career counselor, is needed to align many (career related) matters (15u).* Furthermore, CSPs should be considerate of the ethical guidelines while possessing diverse set of personality characteristics befitting a professional. *The counselor should keep the stuff confidential... the person (student) should be able to trust them in seconds and be able to tell them everything (20u),* mentioned a student while another said, *They are supposed to be very nice (3u).*

Collective effort

To improve CGC services all stake holders should be involved in it. Instead of putting the whole burden on the student or CSP alone, multiple entities should be collaborating for CGC provision. Students, their parents, career counselor, university faculty, university authorities and industry representatives should all be the part of this process. Students can share their problems; parents can share their expectations; CSP can work with them to resolve their concerns; faculty can share their observations about the students' potential and behavior; authorities can render their support and industry representatives can communicate the market demands. Comment of a CSP sums it up, *It is a square shape, industry, academia, student, counselor. This square shape should work together so that we can have more fruitful people in our industry and community (C4).*

Regular and Mandatory CGC

CGC services should be planned at regular intervals. CGC should be spread out at multiple occasions during the four years of under-graduation. It is not very fruitful to indulge in emergency style CGC just before graduation. A student stated, *We have an orientation week. Similarly we should have a counseling week in which experts from industry should come to provide us counseling at the start of our degree. (It should) not be at the end (of degree), when there is just one week before we have to apply for internships (3u).* Participation of students can be increased further by giving timely notice of upcoming CGC activities and by declaring compulsory attendance for the said activities. A student shared, *If we are having a job fair at the university we are informed one week or 10 days back. Then no that is not enough time to work on that (10u),* while a CSP said, *They (students) should have at least 90% attendance (in career related activities). At least once in a semester they must be doing something under the umbrella of career services (C3).*

CGC could also be introduced as a compulsory subject based on practical tasks only. Doing the practical work would lead students to solve many of their career concerns. A CSP elaborated it in this way, *A subject of career management can be introduced in which there are different stages... Course should not be exam based, but (it should be) activity based. Stuff like self-understanding, entering the industry, meeting with potential*

employers, possible job opportunities, job search techniques (should be included). So it can be having single credit hour or zero credit hour or any other suitable time frame for course (C3).

Promotion of entrepreneurship

One way to widen CGC is to identify, create, promote and communicate entrepreneurial opportunities to the students. In addition to the conventional jobs students should be able to consider entrepreneurship as a viable career option. A CSP stated, *Undergrad students should be made interested in not only jobs but entrepreneurship as well. Entrepreneurship opportunities should be made easy so they can easily reach the plan they had in their head (C4).*

Skill development

CGC should focus on skill development of students. Students need a variety of skills to survive in the ever-changing economy. Skills can be learned in numerous ways including curricular and co-curricular activities as well as exposure to practical work like internships, projects, placements. Additionally skills can also be incorporated in the academic curricula by modifying it and adding suitable practical skills and applications along with the theoretical components. A CSP elaborate this point, *We encourage them, all of them, to participate in different activities so you get to know your skills and abilities. And they usually appear during non-study activities. (Sometimes) they also appear through study (related activities). Skills like group work, team work, working under pressure usually come to the surface during study related activities. But through extra-curricular (activities) other skills and abilities show up like how do they (deal) with people other than their peers, how would they communicate with people in the (job) market, and other such things (C7).*

Bridging academia-industry

Bridging the gap between academia and industry could be another significant method to expand CGC. The academia-industry differences translate to fewer numbers of students meeting the needs of industry. To align academia with industry many steps could be taken including but not limited to industrial visits, talks and sessions by industrial experts and alumni working in various positions in job market, designing curricula according to industrial requirements, communicating industrial demands and expectations to the students, spreading awareness about the actual scenario of job market, promoting degrees with potentially high market demand. A CSP stated, *The best plan is that you make the student aware about the industry, the demand of industry. And there can be a lecture once per week or there must be at least one per month (C4),* while another CSP shared, *You can add industrial visits (for students) (C3).*

Another CSP elaborated the way to streamline academia and industry, *We should have a data bank which should tell us the demand of graduates for different fields in the upcoming years. We should promote some degree programs and discourage other degree programs. Otherwise balance cannot be achieved. To discourage some programs heavy taxes can be imposed on them, amount of fee should be increased, accreditation should be limited; excellency centers can be established and only some institutions who can meet the excellency criteria should be able to offer it to students. To encourage some degrees government can provide loans on zero percent interest to students, their education could be made free, their vocational centers can be established (C3).*

Figure: Venn diagram shows the steps to improve CGC overlapping among various stakeholders

Discussion

This research aimed to find out ways to improve CGC in Pakistan at university level. Twelve methods were identified in the results. Increasing awareness and acceptance of CGC is the first and foremost path to CGC improvement. The general public particularly students should be well-informed about potential use and benefits of CGC. Previous literature has covered multiple benefits of CGC like better career decision making and career adaptability (Maree, 2018), enhanced social connections and economic gains (Hooley & Dodd, 2015), improved well being (Robertson, 2013) and purposefulness (Hiebert, Borgan & Schober, 2010). Knowing about these benefits would likely motivate more and more students to avail CGC. University authorities, professionals offering CGC and students can all create and amplify its awareness. Introductory seminars could be conducted; testimonials of beneficiaries could be shared; general reminders could be regularly emailed; ethical guidelines followed by CSPs, particularly about confidentiality and privacy, could be informed to the students; students could motivate fellow students and friends to go for CGC instead of judging them.

Another way to develop CGC is policy making. Comprehensive and appropriate policies should be formulated by the government to promote CGC. Some efforts are recently made by Punjab government as it is promoting career related activities and events in educational institutes (Punjab Higher Education Commission, n.d.) but much more needs to be done. Ministry of education can take steps to embed CGC policy with the educational policy. Such integration of education and CGC would help students to gain maximum benefit from their academia. Various nations in the world have devised and successfully executed their indigenous CGC policies (European Centre for the Development of Vocational Training, n.d.; National Careers Service, n.d.; U.S. Department of Education, 2014). Implementation of CGC policies not only provides governmental support but also helps in streamlining the CGC efforts according to the policy (Richard, 2005). Providing better funding would be another way to enhance CGC. Pakistan hardly spends on CGC (Richard, 2005) but in order to bring improvement, government and universities should allocate funds for CGC. Assigned monetary fund could be used to create specified career centers or offices, to hire more CSPs, to purchase required psychometric tests and assessments, to conduct CGC seminars and activities more often or on larger scales. Funding CGC should be considered as an investment for future of university and its students. When passed out students would easily settle into their careers, it will be a win-win situation for all.

Expanding CGC services could be a way to improve CGC. CGC services should not be limited to a few typical services delivered in a typical manner. Depth and breadth of CGC could be increased in Pakistani universities by offering different services to the students. Both one-to-one sessions and group sessions should be available for students. Workshops, seminars or talks should be arranged on multiple topics including but not limited to CV writing, decision making, time management, professional ethics, job opportunities, entrepreneurship and business opportunities, further studies opportunities, personal development, professional development, self-awareness,

personal skill identification, matching skills to jobs, market and employers' demand etc. Talks by industrial experts and representatives should also be arranged. Websites, applications or other technology can be used to offer information, awareness and guidance to students about themselves, their potential educational journey, prospective careers, potential employers or businesses. Tests and assessments to check IQ, aptitude, interest and personality traits should be available to students. Customized one-to-one session and personal profiling could also be introduced to understand individual differences (Watts & Fretwell, 2004) and offer evidence-based guidance and counseling. International studies have identified numerous CGC services for students (Yoon, Hutchison, Maze, Pritchard, & Reiss, 2018) and efforts must be made to introduce them in Pakistan.

To ascertain maximum utilization of CGC, it is imperative to communicate about the available CGC services. Students should repeatedly receive messages about the CSPs present on their campus, the services offered by them, the dates of CGC events arranged in their university or elsewhere. This could be done through posters and charts displayed on campus, by emails sent to official accounts of students, by sharing scheduled event calendar, by introducing CGC and the CSPs to students on orientation day. Online forums like university website and official social media accounts can also be used to update and remind students about the CGC offered by their university. Publicity of CGC services would reduce the gap between service provider i.e. CSP and the service consumer i.e. students (Garner, Rintz & Valle, 2011). CGC should be perceived as easily approachable by the students. If CGC office or CSP or the procedure of any CGC service is considered to be burdensome, then students refrain from reaching out to it. Therefore, CGC should be an open-for-all service. Establishing contact with CGC office or booking CGC session should not be stressing (Cojocariu & Cojocariu, 2015). Online booking, online contact should be available. CGC office should be at the hub of university so that students need not go out of their way to reach it.

Professionalism of CSPs would also enhance and upgrade CGC at the university level. If the service provider is not professional in their manner and their task, it would deter students from approaching them again (Hiebert & Neault, 2014). CSPs should be qualified to offer CGC; they adhere to the professional code of conduct; they should stick to providing career related help to students by considering their context. Increasing awareness of students by telling them about alternative career options, helping them widen their choices, making them understand about the saturated fields versus in-demand fields are also included in the job of a CSP. Lack of professionalism not only damages the perception of CGC but the service quality as well (American Counseling Association, 2014). In Pakistani universities, many CSPs are not professionally qualified and hence ignorant of the ethical guidelines. It has been observed that basic ethics like confidentiality, privacy, relevant expertise and knowledge are also lacking in some professionals. Such CSPs might be hampering CGC provision instead of strengthening it.

CGC enhancement is not possible by one factor or one member. All relevant stakeholders should make joint effort to uplift CGC. Students should look into available services; CSPs should widen the quality and quantity of CGC services; teachers should cultivate their interest and increase their knowledge about their field; university should support CGC by establishing fully-functioning CGC office; industry should be providing updated information to students and CSPs (Garner, Rintz & Valle, 2011; Hiebert & Neault, 2014). If students are just given admission without considering their aptitude, suitability and future prospects, then it would be merely a business and not appropriate for academia or university culture. Collective synced effort by all would create a synergetic effect, consequently leading to multiplied improvement in CGC. To improve utilization of CGC by the students, CGC services and events should be arranged at regular intervals from the beginning of their university education (Long & Hubble, 2017). Mandatory attendance at such events would push more students to attend them. Making CGC regular and mandatory would increase the interaction of students with them. Information shared at these events will help the students to define and develop their careers.

CGC could also be improved by promoting entrepreneurship for students. As entrepreneurship is rising in Pakistan, more and more students would be interested in entrepreneurial options in addition to job related options for their careers. If CGC office provides them the required information and opportunities about entrepreneurship by arranging expert sessions with indigenous entrepreneurs, it would attract greater number of students. It could do wonders for enhancing the local economy as well as strengthening the name of the institution. International universities have also increased their focus on entrepreneurial activities (Dodgson & Gann, 2020; Zarate-Hoyos & Larios-Meño, 2015). One of the many ways for improving CGC is focusing on skill development of students. CGC office should not only offer information, it should also provide opportunities to students for developing and polishing their skills. This could be done by holding activity-based events, by informing students of skill

development opportunities like internships and projects (Rehill, Kashedpakdel & Mann, 2017). Skill development would also attract those students who prefer hands-on tasks instead of general information-based sessions. Skills demanded by industry also keep on changing (Rainie & Anderson, 2017). So focusing on the upcoming skills would be beneficial for students as well as university and industry.

If gaps between academia and industry are bridged, it would be helpful in improving the status of CGC. When academic studies and CGC sessions fail to inform students about the industrial demand and reality of job market they feel cheated when they arrive at their workplace (Litoiu & Oproiu, 2012). Authentic information about trending industries and upcoming jobs, requirements of employer, linking academic information with practical work of industry would help in decreasing the gaps (Buzzeo & Cifci, 2017; Hooley, 2014). Students would make smoother transitions from university to their workplace.

CONCLUSION

It is concluded that several ways exist for bringing improvement in CGC at university level in Pakistan. This research provides ground for planning and executing practical steps for advancement of CGC. Potential role of students, CSPs, university authorities, industrial representatives, employers and the government has also been indicated. Some steps for CGC improvement need forethought like policy making, whereas other steps could be taken immediately like awareness and acceptance. Improvement in CGC could be the beginning of multi-faceted benefits in the short and long term.

Recommendations and implications

CGC should be accepted, utilized and promoted in the general public through awareness sessions and campaigns. CGC services should be broadened to include the most recent and most relevant topics like entrepreneurship and upcoming skills. Annual schedule consisting of diverse CGC activities and events should be planned and shared with students. Regular reminders should be sent to students or attendance should be made compulsory for the students. To promote one to one counseling, procedure to book the counseling session should be made smooth and easy. One way could be to design or link their official student portal to the CGC office. Available open slots could be visible to students and students could book counseling session for a suitable time slot through the online portal.

Relevant psychological tests should be available for students. Personal career profiles should also be prepared for students. Professionals and experts should be available for counseling, consultation, guidance and advice. Current and future market trends should be known so that students could be guided accordingly. Experience of CGC should be wholesome and welcoming for the students. Open-door policies should be practiced by the CSPs. Non-professional attitudes and practices should be banished; strict compliance to ethical standards should be practiced. University education should be interlaced with skills and practical work. Close connection between academia and industry must be fostered to create more opportunities for practical exposure of students like industrial visits, internships, projects with real-world applications, expert mentoring etc. Government and university authorities should focus on devising policies for CGC.

Educationists and industrial experts must be consulted for making practically beneficial policy frameworks. Resources and funds should also be allocated to execute those policies. Professional standards and policies for CSPs should also be chalked out. Indigenous experts, international experts, international standards and best practices, local culture, need and utility of CGC at university level are some of the factors which should be considered while devising indigenous standards for the profession. Current research also opens many avenues for future research. Further studies could focus on the efficacy of current CGC services. Effectiveness of professional and non-professional CGC practices could be studied. Longitudinal research design could be used to gather evidence about effects of CGC over a long duration.

Limitations

This research included the view point of students and CSPs only. University authorities, members from industries and government representatives were not interviewed regarding their stance on CGC improvement.

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